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THE PROBLEM OF ASSESSING EFFECTIVENESS OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL SOCIALIZATION

The article is devoted to the analyses of the specific features of students' professional socialization in Ukrainian universities. The following approaches to the selection of the criteria of professional socialization effectiveness have been identified: objective indicators of changes in the personality of a student receiving a higher education (the scope of the student's professional skills, the knowledge gained; his/her degree of professional development, self-realization, etc.); subjective characteristics (the student's professional self-identification and self-awareness).

The criteria for professional socialization assessment (educational and professional, social and personal) are considered. In accordance with those criteria, three approaches to the role and results of professional socialization are reviewed: subject – object, subject – subject, and the identification approach.

It is shown that professional socialization is determined by a chain of factors of social and professional environment which significantly affects students' choice of their professional behavior pattern.

Key words: students' professional socialization, effectiveness of professional socialization, criteria of professional socialization, assessing effectiveness of professional socialization.

Зверко Т. В., Тарасова О. В. Проблема оцінки ефективності професійної соціалізації студентів

Стаття присвячена аналізу особливостей та проблем професійної соціалізації студентів в українських вишах.

Виділені наступні підходи до проблеми вибору критеріїв ефективності професійної соціалізації: в основі – об'єктивні показники змін особистості студента в процесі здобуття вищої освіти (сформованість професійних навичок, наявність знань тощо; розвиток особистості студента, його самореалізація); в якості критерію – суб'єктивні характеристики (професійна самоідентифікація і самосвідомість студента).

Представлено критерії успішності професійної соціалізації у ЗВО (навчально-професійні, соціальні й особистісні).

Згідно з обґрунтованими критеріями роль і результати професійної

соціалізації розглянуто з точки зору трьох підходів: суб'єкт – об'єктного, суб'єкт – суб'єктного, ідентифікаційного.

Виявлено, що процес соціалізації та професіоналізації особистості залежить від низки об'єктивних та суб'єктивних чинників соціально-професійного середовища, які суттєво впливають на вибір студентами прийнятних для них соціально-професійних зразків поведінки.

Ключові слова: професійна соціалізація, професійна соціалізація студентів, ефективність професійної соціалізації, критерії професійної соціалізації, оцінка ефективності професійної соціалізації.

Зверко Т. В., Тарасова Е. В. Проблема оценки эффективности профессиональной социализации студентов

Статья посвящена анализу особенностей и проблем профессиональной социализации студентов в украинских вузах.

Выделены подходы к проблеме выбора критериев эффективности профессиональной социализации: в основе – объективные показатели изменений личности студента в процессе получения высшего образования (сформированность профессиональных навыков, наличие знаний и т.д.; развитие личности студента, его самореализация); в качестве критерия – субъективные характеристики (профессиональная самоидентификация и самосознание студента).

Представлены критерии успешности профессиональной социализации в вузе (учебно-профессиональные, социальные и личностные).

В соответствии с обоснованными критериями роль и результаты профессиональной социализации рассмотрены с точки зрения трех подходов: субъект – объектного, субъект – субъектного, идентификационного.

Виявлено, що процес соціалізації та професіоналізації личности зависит от ряда объективных и субъективных факторов социально-профессиональной среды, которые существенно влияют на выбор студентами социально-профессиональных образцов поведения.

Ключевые слова: профессиональная социализация, профессиональная социализация студентов, эффективность профессиональной социализации, критерии профессиональной социализации, оценка эффективности профессиональной социализации.

Recent tendencies in the development of society (expansion of service industry, lengthening of the terms of learning, and the extremely high

educational qualifications of the post-industrial society) prolonged the period of individuals' transition to adulthood. As Yu. G. Volkov points out, «... young people of about 20 or older can choose for themselves some transitional social institutions, ... they become less dependent financially, acquire new social roles, become more independent and responsible... Their working experience gives them their first perception of themselves as adults..., they acquire an ability to form relationships with other persons based on trust ...» [1]. In other words, for young people, especially students, socialization connected with professional activities becomes of great significance.

One of the important dimensions of socialization at university is professional socialization, which is the leading function of higher education [2; 3; 4]. It is during this period that a young person develops the basic professional views and attainments, and comes to realize that his/her success in their future professional career depends on the «right» start ensured by university education.

The socializing role of a higher institution of learning is not reduced to the content of education only, it also implies adaptation to university environment and planning the person's expected social and professional status in the future. The nature of such socialization is influenced by both internal (the institution's faculty and staff, their professional qualifications, the socio-psychological climate in the organization, its material and technical base, their methodological support of the educational process, the students' environment, etc.), and external conditions (political and socio-economic situation in the region and the country at large, high or low prestige of higher education, the rating given to the given institution by the public, etc.).

Successful socialization at university is the first step in a person's professional and their further career building effectiveness. This makes the problem of assessing the effectiveness of socialization a topical enough problem. In this connection, it seems expedient to analyze the various concepts of *socialization* effectiveness and suggest their typology.

The purpose of the present research is to explicate the criteria of professional socialization assessment.

Analyzing the existing views on the problem, one can identify the following approaches to the selection of professional socialization effectiveness [5; 6; 7; 8]:

1. Objective indicators of changes in the personality of a university student (the scope of the student's professional skills, the knowledge gained; his/her degree of professional development, self-realization, etc.).

2. Subjective indicators of changes in the personality of a university student (the student's professional and personality self-identification and self-awareness).

Within the framework of the subjective-objective approach to education (ссылки?) specialization is defined as formation of the features corresponding to the status and the requirements set by society or as adoption of the existing requirements (for the future professional role, requirements for professional knowledge and skills).

From the point of view of the subjective-objective approach, socialization does not only imply adaptation of the individual to society but also his/her self-development and self-realization. Personal development is understood as a process of wholesome development of a student as a subject of professional activities, determined by the learning process organization and the student's own activity [9, p. 68].

Within the subjective-subjective approach, specialization means an ability of changing one's value orientations, ability of finding a balance between one's own values and the requirements of the adopted role, orientation at an understanding of a person's universal moral values (respect for people, ability to predict the future, flexibility in adapting to changing circumstances, creativity).

G. Raven has introduced the concept of «competence», which is not limited to intellectual and other abilities but also presupposes a person's inner motivation for achieving significant goals. To the constituent components of competence, he also refers an ability of a clearer understanding of values, self-control, readiness and willingness to learn independently, self-confidence, critical thinking, ingenuity, openness to new ideas and innovations, ability to bear personal responsibility, aptitude for teamwork, etc. [9, p. 83].

If the change of the individual's social status and adopting new roles

are objective indicators of the socialization process, social identity is a subjective one.

Of special interest to us is a definition of professional identity. According to S.G. Razuvayev, it is a process of establishing identity between the «Professional Me» and an ideal image of “Me carrying out my professional activities in an optimal way, adopting the norms and values of one’s professional community» [9, p. 43].

As contemporary research shows (S. A. Druzhilova, Ye.G. Yefremova, Zh. P Pavlova, N. G. Rukavishnikova, D. V. Shlyakova and others), students’ professional identity is formed gradually and is not always stable. It is becoming more objective as the student obtains true information about the nature of the chosen professional activities, his/her own social role and his/her own compliance with the requirements of the profession.

Professional identity is based on the following kinds of knowledge: belonging to a professional community; degree of one’s conformity to professional standards, awareness of one’s place in the system of social «roles»; degree of having recognition one has achieved in his/her professional group; one’s strengths and weaknesses; individual ways of achieving success.

Within the framework of the subjective-objective approach, socialization is considered to be successful only if a university graduate has assimilated the full scope of knowledge prescribed by the corresponding educational standards and is working in the field he/she has been trained in.

Within the subjective-subjective approach, which assigns an important role to self-realization and personality development (including professional development), socialization can be considered successful, if, in the course of studies, the student has been able to get an awareness of his/her interests and needs and found, upon graduation, his/her own niche on the labor market.

From the structural point of view, the criteria of successful socialization, according to M. V. Migacheva, include: the criteria of successful professional socialization recognized by students themselves, as well as by secondary professional socialization agents (administrators, specialists).

Professional socialization self-evaluation by young specialists consists of the following indicators: 1) motivation in the choice of profession;

2) developing qualities necessary for performing successful professional activities; 3) dealing effectively with professional adaptation problems; 4) exploiting career-growth possibilities in the organization; 5) using professional growth possibilities in the organization; 6) using career-growth factors in the organization; 7) considering possible reasons for changing jobs; 8) using professional socialization agents' authority; 9) enjoying a degree of self-realization freedom; 10) using the knowledge of the etiquette and everyday practices both in the work collective and society at large; 11) being aware of one's own social status [7, p. 111].

Evaluation of young specialists' professional socialization by secondary professional socialization agents (administrators, specialists) can be structurally divided into the following indices: 1) institutional characteristics of the social organization; 2) young specialists working conditions; 3) agents' interaction with young specialists; 4) perception of the abilities and skills necessary for successful professional socialization [7, p. 114].

Some scholars also argue that young specialists' habits of self-organization and self-management are not fully formed yet, which slows down the process of their professional socialization [5; 6]. The main problems in this respect are connected with a lack of team-work experience and moral and ethic qualities of young specialists.

The complex structure of a person's professional socialization predetermines the complex nature of its effectiveness assessment [6], which includes professional, social and personal criteria. The professional criteria include: cognitive and professional motivation; understanding of the content of education; understanding of the instrumental foundations of professional activities; professional competencies formation. The set of social criteria consists of: conformity of societal requirements to specialists of the given profession; formation of the specialist' socio-civil qualities, sufficient for the fulfillment of professional functions; general cultural level; the person's adequate collaboration with other people in the working collective. The complex of personal criteria includes: formation of professional activities base of motivational values; basic elements of professional identity; satisfaction with the choice of profession, with the process of obtaining professional education and future professional life; readiness for professional self-development.

Conclusions. An individual's socialization is of integral nature, having both spiritual and instrumental characteristics, and is of significance for both the individual and society. The particular features of socialization in a higher educational institution are determined by internal, as well as external factors.

Professional socialization is understood, on the one hand, as a process of an individual's entering the professional milieu, accumulation of professional experience, of the standards and values of the professional community, on the other hand, as a process of active realization of the accumulated professional experience.

In conformity with the criteria identified in this article, the rope and outcomes of professional socialization are regarded from the point of view of the subject-object, subject-subject and identification approaches.

The complex structure of professional socialization has determined the complex nature of its effectiveness assessment. The criteria of successful professional socialization can be professional, social and personal.

References

1. Волков Ю. Г. Социология [Электронный ресурс] / Ю. Г. Волков, В. И. Добренъков. – М., 2003.– Режим доступа: http://sbiblio.com/biblio/archive/volkov_sociologija. – Загл. с экрана.
2. Чепак В. В. Теоретико-методологічні засади становлення і розвитку соціології освіти: монографія / В. Чепак. – Київ : Вид-во ТОВ «Геопринт», 2011. – 304 с.
3. Шаронова С. А. Универсальные константы института образования – механизм воспроизводства общества / С. Шаронова. – М. : Изд-во Рос. ун-та дружбы народов. – 2004. – 357 с.
4. Sociology of education in Ukraine / В. И. Астахова, Е. Г. Михайлева, Е. В. Батаева, В. Матвеев // Global sociology of education / Новгород. гос. ун-т им. Ярослава Мудрого. – Великий Новгород ; М., 2013.
5. Валеева И. А. Критерии и показатели качества подготовки специалиста в педагогическом вузе [Электронный ресурс] / И. А. Валеева. – Режим доступа: <http://www.t21.kgups.ru/doc/2009/10/02.doc> – Загл. с экрана.
6. Вирина И. В. Конкурентоспособность молодых специалистов по оценкам руководителей / И. В. Вирина // Социальная политика и социология. – 2007. – № 2. – С. 174–177.

7. Мигачева М. В. Институциональный механизм профессиональной социализации молодых специалистов в современном российском обществе : дис. ... канд. социол. наук : 22.00.04 / М. В. Мигачева. – Ставрополь, 2008. – 211 с.

8. Назарова Л. В. Формирование карьерных стратегий личности в процессе социализации / Л. В. Назарова // Общество и право. – 2011. – № 3. – С. 21–28.

9. Разуваев С. Г. Модель профессиональной социализации будущего специалиста технического профиля в условиях многоуровневого образовательного комплекса [Электронный ресурс] / С. Г. Разуваев. – Режим доступа: <http://ej.kubagro.ru/2013/01/pdf/31.pdf>. – Загл. с экрана.

References

1. Volkov YU. G. Sotsiologiya [Elektronnyy resurs] / YU. G. Volkov, V. I. Dobren'kov. – M., 2003. – Rezhim dostupa: http://sbiblio.com/biblio/archive/volkov_sociologija. – Zagl. s ekrana.

2. Chepak V. V. Teoretiko-metodologichnii zasady stanovleniya i razvitiya sotsiologii osviti: monografiya / V. Chepak. – Київ : Вид-во ТОВ «Geoprint», 2011. – 304 с.

3. Sharonova S. A. Universal'nyye konstanty instituta obrazovaniya – mekhanizm vosпроизводства obshchestva / S. Sharonova. – M.: Izd-vo Ros. un-ta druzhby narodov. – 2004. – 357 s.

4. Sociology of education in Ukraine / V. I. Astakhova, Ye. G. Mikhayleva, Ye. V. Batayeva, V. Matveyev // Global sociology of education / Novgorod. gos. un-tim. Yaroslava Mudrogo. – Velikiy Novgorod ; M., 2013.

5. Valeyeva I. A. Kriterii i pokazateli kachestva podgotovki spetsialista v pedagogicheskom vuze [Elektronnyy resurs] / I. A. Valeyeva. – Rezhim dostupa: <http://www.t21.kgups.ru/doc/2009/10/02.doc> – Zagl. s ekrana.

6. Virina I. V. Konkurentosposobnost' molodykh spetsialistov po otsenkam rukovoditeley / I. V. Virina // Sotsial'naya politika i sotsiologiya. – 2007. – № 2. – S. 174–177.

7. Migacheva M. V. Institutsional'nyy mekhanizm professional'noy sotsializatsii molodykh spetsialistov v sovremennom rossiyskom obshchestve : dis. ... kand. sotsiol. nauk : 22.00.04 / M. V. Migacheva – Stavropol', 2008. – 211 s.

8. Nazarova L. V. Formirovaniye kar'yernykh strategiy lichnosti v protsesse sotsializatsii / L. V. Nazarova // Obshchestvo i pravo. – 2011. – № 3. – S. 21–28.

9. Razuvayev S. G. Model' professional'noy sotsializatsii budushchogo spetsialista tekhnicheskogo profilya v usloviyakh mnogourovnevnogo obrazovatel'nogo kompleksa [Elektronnyy resurs] / S. G. Razuvayev. – Rezhim dostupa: <http://ej.kubagro.ru/2013/01/pdf/31.pdf>. – Zagl. s ekrana.